

Orange juice-HCl catalyzed efficient green route for Biginelli reaction under solvent free condition by grinding method

Vaibhav P. Landage*¹, Jyoti T. Waghmode¹, Supriya S. Deokate¹ and Harshad J. Salunkhe¹

¹Department of Chemistry, Anekant Education Society's Tuljaram Chaturchand College, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Baramati, India

*Corresponding Author: Vaibhav P. Landage

Abstract- Biginelli reaction is one pot multicomponent reaction. A green approach grinding is applied for this multicomponent reaction containing aromatic aldehydes 1, ethyl aceto acetate 2 and urea / thiourea 3 catalyzed by few drops of natural Orange juice and C. HCl as catalyst under solvent free condition at room temperature. The catalyst used is simple, ecofriendly and provides good result. Grinding process is economical, time and energy efficient. Resulted products 3, 4-dihyropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones or thiones 4A-K were confirmed by spectral and analytical analysis.

Keywords- Aromatic aldehydes, Ethyl aceto acetate, Thiourea, Urea

I. INTRODUCTION

The Biginelli reaction, first described in 1893, has received recently substantial attention from synthetic and medicinal chemists^[1]. For synthesis of organic compounds, ecofriendly green methods have given much attention. As green chemistry becomes a national priority, the demand for convenient and rapid synthetic procedures that are energy efficient is growing. These procedures should ideally also be suitable for large-scale operations of pharmaceuticals and their intermediates. We apply here a green technique called grindstone chemistry, which is particularly useful for desktop synthesis. Toda et al.'s pioneering work confirmed that several reactions can be conceded out with high yields simply by grinding solids together^[2], though typically on a small scale using an agate mortar and pestle. Multi-component reactions (MCRs), where three or more reactants combine in a single pot to form a product that incorporates structural elements from each reagent^[3], are particularly noteworthy. MCRs are a

powerful tool in organic chemistry, attracting significant attention^[4]. Biginelli's original method involved the acid-catalyzed, one-pot reaction of an aryl aldehyde, ethyl acetoacetate, and urea or thiourea, catalyzed by HCl, to synthesize dihydropyrimidones^[5]. In the past decade, numerous methods and catalysts have been developed^[6, 7] for this synthesis. These catalysts^[8] include organic compounds as metal acetates^[9], carboxylic acids^[10], fruit juice^[11], cuttle bone^[12] and inorganic compounds like dehydrated CaSO_4 ^[13], $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ^[14], $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ ^[15], $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ^[16] and MgBr_2 ^[17]. Various methods, such as microwave irradiation^[18] and ultrasound^[19] have also been explored. Dihydropyrimidones have been found to exhibit a wide range of biological activities, including anti-microbial^[20], antihypertensive^[21], anti-HIV^[22], antimalarial^[23], and antibacterial^[24]. Notable drugs containing dihydropyrimidine-2-ones/thiones include Monastrol^[25] (an anticancer drug) and Fluorastrol^[26] (an Eg5 inhibitor). All these reflection endorsed us to synthesize such bioactive dihydropyrimidines-ones / thiones.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Many catalysts and variety of solvent include water; ionic liquids, ethanol and other solvent were used for Biginelli reaction. It was realized that utmost of the solvent and catalysts used are not eco-friendly. We primarily thought about the catalyst by keeping in mind it must be green one. We carried out the reaction at room temperature with few drops of lime juice, c. HCl and equimolar quantities of anisaldehydes, ethyl aceto acetate and urea by grinding mortar and pestle. This procedure gave **4A** compound within 22 minutes with 86 % yield. Our efforts were focused to optimize the method. (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1: Synthesis of 3, 4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones or thiones

In this method we used c. HCl which is the driving catalyst supported by non-processed lime juice containing citric acid (amount in lime juice 5-7 %). The use of supportive catalyst is to minimize the usage of c. HCl. For synthesis of target molecule, equimolar quantities of aryl aldehydes, an ethyl aceto acetate and urea or thiourea with few drops of lime juice and c. HCl were grinded together at room temperature. The physical characterization of synthesized compounds is given in Table 1. The ^1H NMR spectra of **4A**, **4C**, **4E**, **4G**, **4I** and **4K** compounds showed two singlets in the range of δ 9.32-10.34 for two N-H group. They showed triplet for methyl group at δ 1.08-1.31 and quartet for methylene group at δ 3.97-4.01, they also showed one singlet at δ 5.10-5.19 for methyne proton, all these observations of NMR spectra indicates the formation of these products. IR spectra of above illustrious compounds showed two bands at 3201-3110 cm^{-1} for N-H stretching frequency and one band at 1782-1775 for C=O of ester. The compound **4A**, **4C** and **4E** showed single peak of C=O group of amide at the frequency of 1690-1685 cm^{-1} support the creation of these compounds. The compounds **4G**, **4I** and **4K** showed C=S group frequency at the range of 1080-1075 cm^{-1} this further support the formation of these compounds. Mass spectra of above mentioned compounds support their formation. The physical constant of synthesized compounds also in the range as the results are reported in the literature, this further support the formation of these products.

TABLE I

Physical characterization data of synthesized compounds

Compd	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	X	Yield (%)	M.P. (°C)
4A	H	H	OCH ₃	O	86	208–210
4B	H	H	OH	O	89	226–228
4C	H	H	H	O	88	200–202
4D	H	H	CH ₃	O	86	226-228
4E	H	Cl	H	O	87	218-220
4F	H	H	Cl	O	86	210–212
4G	H	H	OCH ₃	S	88	152-154
4H	H	H	OH	S	90	200-202
4I	H	H	H	S	88	208-210

4J	H	H	CH ₃	S	85	196-198
4K	H	Cl	H	S	85	218-220
4L	H	H	Cl	S	87	228-230

III. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

All the chemicals used were commercial available and AR grade. Physical constant were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. IR spectra were verified on a SHIMADZU FT-IR spectrophotometer and Mass spectra were recorded on a TOF MS ES+ 1.09e6. ¹H spectra on a BRUKER AVANCE NEO 500 NMR spectrometer with DMSO-*d*₆ as a solvent and chemical shift (δ) are expressed in ppm with internal standard TMS.

General procedure-

Synthesis of 3, 4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones or thiones 4A-K

Equimolar quantities of aryl aldehydes (0.01 moles), an ethyl aceto acetate (0.01 moles) and urea or thiourea (0.01 moles) with 3-4 drops of lime juice and 2-3 drops of c. HCl were grinded together in mortar and pestle for 20-30 minutes at room temperature. The improvement of the reaction was checked by TLC. After completion of reaction, resultant was poured into cold water with stirring and then filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

4A: Ethyl 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-2-oxopyrimidine-5-carboxylate

IR (KBr Pellet, ν , cm^{-1}): 3197 (N-H), 3118 (N-H), 2880 (C-H), 1780 (C=O, ester), 1689 (C=O, amide); Mass: m/z 290 $[\text{M}]^+$; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.31 (t, 3H, CH₃), 2.65 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.68 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 3.96 (q, 2H, CH₂), δ 5.09 (s, 1H, C-H), 6.84 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.10 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 9.55 (s, 1H, N-H), 10.21 (s, 1H, N-H); Elemental Analysis, Found, %: C 62.08; H 6.28; N 9.6. C₁₅H₁₈O₄N₂. Calculated, %: C 62.06; H 6.25; N 9.65.

4C: Ethyl 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro-6-methyl-2-oxo-4-phenylpyrimidine-5-carboxylate

IR (KBr Pellet, ν , cm^{-1}): 3196 (N-H), 3110 (N-H), 2884 (C-H), 1775 (C=O, ester), 1690 (C=O, amide); Mass: m/z 260 $[\text{M}]^+$; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.12 (t, 3H, CH₃), 2.32 (s, 3H, CH₃), 4.20 (q, 2H, CH₂), δ 5.17 (s, 1H, C-H), 7.26 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 9.62 (s, 1H, N-H), 10.34 (s, 1H, N-H); Elemental Analysis, Found, %: C 64.62; H 6.18; N 10.78. C₁₄H₁₆O₃N₂. Calculated, %: C 64.60; H 6.20; N 10.76.

4E: Ethyl 4-(3-chlorophenyl)-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro-6-methyl-2-oxopyrimidine-5-carboxylate

IR (KBr Pellet, ν , cm^{-1}): 3198 (N-H), 3114 (N-H), 2894 (C-H), 1782 (C=O, ester), 1685 (C=O, amide); Mass: m/z 294 $[\text{M}]^+$, 296 $[\text{M}+2]^+$; ¹H NMR (500MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.08 (t, 3H, CH₃), 2.24 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.98 (q, 2H, CH₂), δ 5.14 (s, 1H, C-H), 7.24 (d, 1H, Ar-H), 7.29 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.36 (d, 1H, Ar-H), 7.39 (t, 1H, Ar-H), 9.36 (s, 1H, N-H), 10.32 (s, 1H, N-H); Elemental Analysis, Found, %: C 57.07; H 5.15; N 9.52. C₁₄H₁₅O₃N₂Cl. Calculated, %: C 57.05; H 5.13; N 9.50.

4G: Ethyl 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-2-thioxopyrimidine-5-carboxylate

IR (KBr Pellet, ν , cm^{-1}): 3201 (N-H), 3120 (N-H), 2890 (C-H), 1778 (C=O, ester), 1075 (C=S); Mass: m/z 306 $[\text{M}]^+$; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 1.30 (t, 3H, CH₃), 2.67 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.69 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 3.97 (q, 2H, CH₂), δ 5.11 (s, 1H, C-H), 6.86 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.12 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 9.54 (s, 1H, N-H), 10.22 (s, 1H, N-H); Elemental Analysis, Found, %: C 58.82; H 5.93; N 9.16. C₁₅H₁₈O₃N₂S, Calculated, %: C 58.80; H 5.92; N 9.14.

4I: Ethyl 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro-6-methyl-4-phenyl-2-thioxopyrimidine-5-carboxylate

IR (KBr Pellet, ν , cm^{-1}): 3197 (N-H), 3116 (N-H), 2881 (C-H), 1780 (C=O, ester), 1080 (C=S); Mass: m/z 276 $[\text{M}]^+$; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 1.10 (t, 3H, CH_3), 2.30 (s, 3H, CH_3), 4.0 (q, 2H, CH_2), δ 5.19 (s, 1H, C-H), 7.28 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 9.64 (s, 1H, N-H), 10.32 (s, 1H, N-H); Elemental Analysis, Found, %: C 60.84; H 5.82; N 10.12. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$. Calculated, %: C 60.85; H 5.84; N 10.14.

4K: Ethyl 4-(3-chlorophenyl)-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro -6-methyl-2-thioxopyrimidine-5-carboxylate

IR (KBr Pellet, ν , cm^{-1}): 3195 (N-H), 3112 (N-H), 2878 (C-H), 1775 (C=O, ester), 1078 (C=S); Mass: m/z 310 $[\text{M}]^+$; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 1.10 (t, 3H, CH_3), 2.28 (s, 3H, CH_3), 4.01 (q, 2H, CH_2), 5.10 (s, 1H, C-H), 7.22 (d, 1H, Ar-H), 7.27 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.32 (d, 1H, Ar-H), 7.37 (t, 1H, Ar-H), 9.32 (s, 1H, N-H), 10.30 (s, 1H, N-H); Elemental Analysis, Found, %: C 54.12; H 4.88; N 9.03. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}\text{Cl}$. Calculated, %: C 54.10; H 4.86; N 9.01.

IV. CONCLUSION

The used catalysts contain few drops of Orange juice which is cheap, natural and ecological. This technique is safe, simple, and economic and gives worthy yield with atom economy and less reaction time at room temperature. This method gives solvent and energy free green route for Biginelli reaction.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Biginelli P. G. Synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidine-2(1H)- ones, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, **1893**, 23, 360-416.
- [2] Toda F.; Tanaka K.; Sekikawa A. Host-Guest complex formation by a solid-solid reaction, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, **1987**, 279-280.
- [3] Armstrong R. M.; Combs A. P.; Tempest P. A.; Brown S. D.; Keating T. A. Multiple component condensation strategies for combinatorial library synthesis, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, **1996**, 29, 123-131.
- [4] Domling A. Recent developments in isocyanide based multicomponent reactions in applied chemistry, *Chem. Rev.*, **2006**, 106, 17-89.
- [5] Biginelli P. G.; Aldureides of ethylic acetoacetate and ethylic oxalacetate, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, **1893**, 23, 360-416.
- [6] Bigi F.; Carloni S.; Frullanti B.; Maggi R.; Sartori G. A Revision of the Biginelli reaction under solid acid catalysis. Solvent-free synthesis of dihydropyrimidines over montmorillonite KSF, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, **1999**, 40, 3465-3468.
- [7] Ranu B. C.; Hajra A.; and Jana U. Indium (III) Chloride-catalyzed one-pot synthesis of dihydropyrimidinones by a three-component coupling of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds, aldehydes, and urea: An improved procedure for the Biginelli reaction, *J. Org. Chem.*, **2000**, 65, 6270-6272.

- [8] Kolosov M. A.; Orlov V. D.; Beloborodov D. V.; Dotsenko V. V. A chemical placebo: NaCl as an effective, cheapest, non-acidic and greener catalyst for Biginelli-type 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones (-thiones) synthesis, *Mol Divers*, **2009**, 13, 5-25.
- [9] Karamat A.; Khan M. A.; Sharif A. Metal acetate mediated Biginelli one-pot synthesis, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, **2010**, 57, 1099-1101.
- [10] Noreen S.; Perveen S.; Khan M. N.; Nazeer A.; Khan M. A.; Munawar M. A.; Babar R.; Sohail F.; Azad M.; Bernardino A. M. R.; Dos Santos M. S. Biginelli reaction-Carboxylic acids as catalysts, *Asian J. Chem.*, **2013**, 25, 4770-4772.
- [11] Kale A. A. Green synthesis and characterization of dihydropyrimidinone derivatives using fruit juice, *Curr. Pharm. Res.*, **2019**, 9(3), 2854-2858.
- [12] Firoozeh N.; Rezazadeh S.; Izanloo C. A green synthesis of 3, 4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones via one-pot multi-component reaction by using cuttlebone as a natural catalyst under solvent free condition, *J. Mex. Chem. Soc.*, **2017**, 61(3), 241-249.
- [13] Boumoud T.; Boumoud B.; Mosset P.; Debache A. Gypsum-catalyzed one pot synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones under solvent-free conditions, *E. J. Chem.*, **2011**, 8(1), 312-318.
- [14] Wang D. C.; Guo H. M.; Qu G. R. Efficient, green, solvent-free synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones via Biginelli reaction catalyzed by Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O, *Synth. Commun.*, **2010**, 40(8), 1115-1122.
- [15] Ramachandiran N.; Sumathi S.; Buvaneswari G. Study of catalytic activity of ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate in the synthesis of 3,4- Dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones, *Indian J. Chem.*, **2009**, 48(B), 865-867.
- [16] Pathak V. N.; Gupta R.; Varshney B. An efficient, inexpensive 'Green Chemistry' route to multicomponent Biginelli condensation catalyzed by CuCl₂·2H₂O-HCl, *Indian J. Chem.*, **2008**, 47(B), 434-438.
- [17] Hojatollah S.; Qing-Xiang G. Efficient magnesium bromide-catalyzed one pot synthesis of substituted 1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-ones under solvent-free conditions, *Chinese J. Chem.*, **2005**, 23, 91-97.
- [18] Stadler A.; Kappe C. O. Microwave-mediated Biginelli reactions revisited, on the nature of rate and yield Enhancements, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, **2000**, 2, 1363-1368.
- [19] Yadav J. S.; Reddy B. V. S.; Bhaskar Reddy K.; Sarita Raj K.; Prasad A. R. Ultrasound-accelerated synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones with ceric ammonium nitrate, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, **2001**, 1, 1939- 1941.
- [20] Desai N. C.; Joshi S. B.; Jadeja K. A. A one-pot multicomponent Biginelli reaction for the preparation of novel pyrimidinethione derivatives as antimicrobial agents. *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, **2020**, 57, 791-795.
- [21] Zorkun I. S.; Sarac S.; Celebib S.; Erolb K. Synthesis of 4-aryl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-thione derivatives as potential calcium channel blockers, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, **2006**, 14, 8582-8589.
- [22] Agbaje O. C.; Fadeyi O. O.; Fadeyi S. A.; Myles L. E.; Okoro C. O. Synthesis and in vitro cytotoxicity evaluation of some fluorinated hexahydropyrimidine derivatives, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, **2011**, 21, 989-992.

- [23] Chiang A. N.; Valderramos J. C.; Balachandran R.; Chovatiya R. J.; Mead B. P.; Schneider C.; Bell S. L.; Klein M. G.; Huryn D. M.; Chen X. S.; Day B. W.; Fidock D. A.; Wipf P.; Brodsky J. L. Novel selective androgen receptor modulators: SAR studies on 6-bisalkylamino-2-quinolinones, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, **2009**, 17, 1527-1531.
- [24] Chitra S.; Devanathan D.; Pandiarajan K. Synthesis and antioxidant activity evaluation of new hexahydropyrimido[5,4-C]Quinoline-2,5-diones and 2-thioxohexahydropyrimido[5,4-C]Quinoline-5-ones obtained by Biginelli reaction in two steps, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, **2010**, 45, 367-371.
- [25] Mayer T. U.; Kapoor T. M.; Haggarty S. J.; King R. W.; Schreiber S. L.; Mitchison T. J. Small molecule inhibitor of mitotic spindle bipolarity identified in a phenotype-based screen, *Science*, **1999**, 286, 971-974.
- [26] Kaan H. Y. K.; Ulaganathan V.; Rath O.; Prokopcov H.; Dallinger D.; Kappe C. O.; Kozielski F. Structural basis for inhibition of Eg5 by dihydropyrimidines: stereoselectivity of antimetabolic inhibitors enastron, dimethylenastron and Fluorastrol, *J. Med. Chem.*, **2010**, 53, 5676-5683.